

Ransomware: Attack, Human Impact and Mitigation

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Abstract - Ransomware is one of the types of malware which is the result of sophisticated effort to compromise the modern computer structures. In this paper we examine the current history of ransomware and its growth to the recent form of large-scale ransomware attacks (ones that interrupt whole organizations). Within that timeframe, public reporting, articles, and news media reporting on large-scale ransomware attacks is reviewed to create an experimental analysis of ransom payments, circumstances that led to those payments, and if data was eventually recovered through a literature study for the people victimized by ransomware. Increasing threats due to ease of transfer of ransomware over internet are also talk over. Finally, low level awareness among company professionals is confirmed and reluctance to payment on being a victim is found as a common trait.

Keywords- Ransomware; Extortion; Malware

I. INTRODUCTION

Ransomware is a type of malware that creates files on a victim's computer isolated and then demands the victim to pay a ransom (commonly in the method of bitcoins) in order to recover access to the lost files. In 2013, the first popular conventional ransomware called Crypto locker spread through the Internet [1]. Since then, the threat and danger has grown-up and is now a common-place incident constructing headlines regularly. Among the concerns that are frequently expressed is the ethical concerns of giving ransoms and how persons who do pay are merely funding the next attacks. On one hand, limited the profitability of such attacks would lessen their occurrence. On the other hand, it would need organizations to agree the permanent loss of data or to be potentially shut down permanently.

II. IMPACT OF RANSOMWARE:

Generally, ransomware attack is seen from the prism of business, commercial and financial environments. The ransom is monetary, and the costs involved with recovery are monetary [1]. Ransomware utilizes techniques to inforce victim into paying the demanded quantity in Bitcoins (usually undetectable Crypto Currency) or providing personal information. Still, there are many times in which files aren't decrypted even after a charge has been paid. The ultra-modern consensus is that ransomware maintains in vital categories which may be crypto and locker [2]. This contains that the victim retaining of the laptop machine is done by way of both encrypting documents and locking the computer or by either one of them.

In a subset of cases, a ransom payment may mean the difference among a business continuing to exist or to close. There are also other non-financial interests to consider. A modern study into the effects of ransomware attacks on hospitals indicated that hospitals that suffered breaches as well as ransomware frequently had longer times to given that critical services that has led to a measurable growth in mortality rates of those services compared to those that did not suffer a breach or ransomware infection. Government organizations were more likely to not pay the ransom as finish is not a possible effect for them. There is also the individual impact of executives in charge of IT or IT security on their future careers and the intangible costs to organizations for reputational damage that may occurs as being identified as a victim of ransomware [1]. Although difficult to calculate, those making selections in addressing ransomware have the clear real costs mentioned above, they are likely to involve in choices that do not badly disturb their employability or company's future reputation unnecessarily. It is practical to accept the cause that most public reports for ransomware attacks involve certain industries is that many have no choice to report

and have the capability to hide the disruption from the public, thus they have no reason to reveal.

III. ANALYSIS:

Targets which can, from the attacker’s opinion, be seen as feasible targets are a minor subset of the total group of victims. Feasible targets are victims who have lost important data, need the technical skills to make a payment and are also ready to do so. It can consequently be assumed that most ransomware distributors use a ‘shotgun approach’ in the hope of finding some feasible targets and, in practice, create a lot of cyber damage. The Internet provides the key role in pressing threat for easier spread of ransomware.

Some of the statistics of Ransomware highlights the interesting variations. Revealing about their focus where they see greatest opportunity for return, and also variations in countries in their ransomware defenses [4].

Figure 2. Organization Hit Ransomware

Figure 1. Countries Hit Ransomware

Figure 3. Countries Paid Ransomware

IV. RANSOMWARE ATTACKS TYPES, WORKING FUNCTIONALITIES

TABLE I. TYPE

	TYPE
<i>WANNACRY</i>	Cryptowarm
<i>GRANCRAB</i>	Ransomware-as-a-Service (Raas)
<i>SAMSAM</i>	Automated Active Adversary
<i>DHARMA</i>	Automated Active Adversary
<i>BITPAYMER</i>	Automated Active Adversary
<i>RYUK</i>	Automated Active Adversary
<i>LOCKERGOGA</i>	Automated Active Adversary
<i>MEGACORTAX</i>	Automated Active Adversary
<i>ROBBINHOOD</i>	Automated Active Adversary
<i>SODINOKIBI</i>	Automated Active Adversary
<i>NETWALKER</i>	Ransomware-as-a-Service (Raas)

TABLE II. PRIVILEGES ESCALATION

	PRIVILEGES ESCALATION
<i>WANNACRY</i>	Exploit
<i>GRANCRAB</i>	Credentials
<i>SAMSAM</i>	Credentials
<i>DHARMA</i>	Credentials
<i>BITPAYMER</i>	Exploit
<i>RYUK</i>	Credentials
<i>LOCKERGOGA</i>	Credentials
<i>MEGACORTAX</i>	Credentials
<i>ROBBINHOOD</i>	Credentials
<i>SODINOKIBI</i>	Exploit
<i>NETWALKER</i>	Exploit

TABLE III. CIPHER

	CIPHER
<i>WANNACRY</i>	No
<i>GRANCRAB</i>	No
<i>SAMSAM</i>	No
<i>DHARMA</i>	No
<i>BITPAYMER</i>	No
<i>RYUK</i>	No
<i>LOCKERGOGA</i>	Yes
<i>MEGACORTAX</i>	Yes
<i>ROBBINHOOD</i>	No
<i>SODINOKIBI</i>	No
<i>NETWALKER</i>	No

TABLE IV. FILE ENCRYPTION

	FILE ENCRYPTION
<i>WANNACRY</i>	Copy, in place
<i>GRANCRAB</i>	In-Place
<i>SAMSAM</i>	Copy
<i>DHARMA</i>	Copy
<i>BITPAYMER</i>	In-Place
<i>RYUK</i>	In-Place
<i>LOCKERGOGA</i>	In-Place
<i>MEGACORTAX</i>	In-Place
<i>ROBBINHOOD</i>	Copy
<i>SODINOKIBI</i>	In-Place
<i>NETWALKER</i>	In-Place

TABLE V. RENAME

	RENAME
<i>WANNACRY</i>	After the attack
<i>GRANCRAB</i>	After the attack
<i>SAMSAM</i>	After the attack
<i>DHARMA</i>	After the attack
<i>BITPAYMER</i>	After the attack
<i>RYUK</i>	After the attack
<i>LOCKERGOGA</i>	Before the attack
<i>MEGACORTAX</i>	Before the attack
<i>ROBBINHOOD</i>	After the attack
<i>SODINOKIBI</i>	After the attack
<i>NETWALKER</i>	After the attack

TABLE VI. ENCRYPTION BY PROXY

	ENCRYPTION BY PROXY
<i>WANNACRY</i>	No
<i>GRANCRAB</i>	Yes
<i>SAMSAM</i>	No
<i>DHARMA</i>	No
<i>BITPAYMER</i>	No
<i>RYUK</i>	Yes
<i>LOCKERGOGA</i>	No
<i>MEGACORTAX</i>	Yes
<i>ROBBINHOOD</i>	No
<i>SODINOKIBI</i>	No
<i>NETWALKER</i>	No

V. RANSOMWARE ATTACKS IN COVID-19

After the 1st quarter of 2020 the entire world is facing COVID-19 pandemic situation and all the organizations regardless that they are public or private, were forced to shift their approach to work from home. This surge in users results in the internet world being turned into an open ground for attackers to testing with malicious tools and to exploit on the organizations with weaker cyber security controls. A massive amount of ransomware was attacked in 2020. This increase is due to a combination of weaker controls on home IT and a higher likelihood of users clicking on COVID-19 themed ransomware lure emails given levels of anxiety [6]

Some of the attacks are given below:

- ColdLock Ransomware
- RangarLocker Ransomware
- Maze Ransomware
- Doppelpaymer Ransomware
- Nemty Ransomware

And many others had hits the OT/IT market to disturb them.

VI. MITIGATION OF THE RANSOMWARE

Mitigation of the ransomware can be performed in several ways: Off-site backups, capable anti-virus software and user training [3]. And the point has come forward that awareness of basic cyber security best practices is particularly low. As such it looks that a lot of improvement can be prepared by educating computer users of how to create safe backups and how to identify threats on the internet. It is also becoming apparent that in a commercial setting mostly users will assume that any computer problem is the responsibility of the IT department. Whilst this notation is indeed acceptable to some extent, but this attitude has also leads to carelessness and irresponsible behavior. Therefore, firms could most certainly benefit from training their employees in basic cyber security practices.

VII. IF YOU ARE THE VICTIM OF RANSOMWARE ATTACK:

If you suffer a ransomware attack, you must to understand that all credentials currently on these endpoints are now available to attackers, whether the accounts linked with them were active during the attack or not. Determining the effect of a ransomware

attack will not be sufficient because threat performers are identified to change their tools and methods once they can identify their victims' detection abilities. After primary identification has been done the following steps are necessary:

- Quarantine affected system as soon as possible by eliminating the systems from the network or shut down to stop more ransomware attacks all over the network
- Quarantine or Shut down the affected devices that have up till now to be completely corrupted to gain more time to clean and recover data
- Starting backup data and System offline instantly
- All account and network passwords will be change, when the ransomware is removed from the devices/system, you must to change all devices/system/network passwords again.

I was found a website on internet i.e. <https://www.nomoreransom.org/> this website was providing decrypting software free of cost and even though you do not know about the ransomware, you have to just upload a file that was encrypted if there is a decrypting software is available for that encryption technique they will provide it to victim.

VIII. CONCLUSION:

Cybersecurity at that time, faces many type of threat and risk coming regularly from consciously done malware and Cyber-attacks. There are quite a lot of incidents of cyber threat to era and it has on the go disturbing more vital zones such as medicine, energy etc. The latest infamous form of cyber threat is ransomware and this is aiming different zones because it is sophisticated and is an undetectable way to get "easy" money via compromising devices and extorting multimillion budget organizations [2]. The transfer of malware has become easy with increasing Internet based facilities and services. In company environments, high irresponsibility of the employees and dependence on the IT department for malware attacks is confirmed. [3] Hackers have already started to move attention on industries using ransomware nature of attack. Taking access to industry and processes, cyber attackers could become riskier due to the interruption they may impose on the businesses which in turn, may effect to vital procedure and human security of the organizations. Information security

around the world is not sufficient to handle these cyber-attacks and malware, if infection of ransomware spread extremely across the world. The best example of it is WannaCry ransomware that has been attacking worldwide and was only stopped after frequent times of trials by cyber security specialists [5]. However, researching the nomenclature and strategies it is might be possible to be prepared at hand. We could apply those techniques and strategies for defensive and preventive countermeasures and move one step forward.

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